

TRENDS IN CURRENT INTERNATIONAL MIGRATION

Brîndușa Mihaela RADU, PhD Associate Professor

Athenaeum University, Bucharest, Romania

bmradu@yahoo.com

Abstract: *Labor migration is the subject of many specialized studies that are the subject of interdisciplinary sciences such as economics, international affairs, European law, sociology and many others. Due to the evolution of the Romanian economy in recent years, it is important and necessary for any future economist to understand this topic as well as possible (Petrozziello, 2013). Looking ahead, it is necessary to know as much information as possible about the factors underlying the development of the country's economy, as well as about the factors that determine this migration of labor force at international level. If the main reason why at this moment the labor force chose to leave the country of origin and to migrate to the states with a developed economy is a better life, the aim is to provide children with a better future. Worldwide (Katseli et al, 2006), it is currently estimated that there are over 200 million migrants, even the International Day of the Migrant is established, in which this phenomenon has become normal, and in which, mainly, information on human rights is disseminated and to the freedoms of migrants. Nor is Romania outside this framework of international normality, only that the elements of distinction are generated by the reasons for emigration, which, as will be analysed, in a synthetic form, in the following case study, are confined to both economic factors. but, last but not least, the socio-political factors. The paper addresses the problems of international migration and the importance of the migration of the labor force at present on the economic development of a country.*

Keywords: *labor force migration, development, migration theories*

JEL Classification: *J1, J61, C33*

1. Introduction

The phenomenon of migration has always existed and has materialized since the first occurrences of mankind through invasions, transhumance, colonization and crusades, or in general, caused by the attraction of the richer regions over the poorer populations (Iancu, 2011).

Although in the last 10 years in some areas of the world, such as Europe, migration has experienced significant flows, the problem of international migration is a short-term concern for many countries of the world, and is rather a response to some evolutions than to managing or estimating the movement of people. For the European space, the movement of people and of the labor force is of great importance, the enlargement of the EU in successive waves, the demographic aging of the population of (Western)-European countries at an accelerated pace and the economic reasons are the main factors in increasing the movement of the respective people of the labor force (Burian, 2009). Nowadays the demographic preoccupation reappears due to the risks that it arises in the manifestation of crises at local, zonal, continental or planetary level that influence the social order, or in the triggering of disturbances of the ethnic or religious balances.

2. Analysis of theories regarding migration

At present, the phenomenon of international migration is extremely complex, and cannot be included in a single theoretical pattern (Massey, et al, 2012). Due to the free movement within the intra-Community territory, the control of the increasing flow of migrants became very difficult, and in this context, the knowledge of the number and typologies of migrants became a permanent concern of the academic world, the factors of influence, the conditions of unfolding, the reasons for returning to the country. origin or dispersion, constituting subjects of interest for scientific research.

Looking back in time, we find that Ernst Georg Ravenstein, considered the father of migration theories, concluded for the first time that migration was generated by the push-pull process, with the unfavorable conditions of country of origin. Reasons such as low wages, high taxes, repeated abuses of public authorities, legislative instability, unfavourable health climate, unconventional social environment, monopoly trade, or poorly developed transport infrastructure continue to produce migration currents, and at present, because favourable conditions prevail. I attract people from one country to another. The issue of migration has known over time, various theoretical approaches, whose

synthetic presentation we highlight in table 1 (Albu, 2007; Petrozziello, 2013; Katseli, 2006; Massey, et al, 2012) below:

Table 1. Evolutionary presentation of the main theories of migration

The classical theories	Commercialism	Barbon 1690	emigration to the colonies
	Classical school	Smith 1785	displacement of population and capital by abolishing barriers between states
	Marxism	Marx 1867	the needs of displacement and development of the population characterize migration
Push-pull model	Migration laws	Ravenstein 1885	migration was influenced by the push-pull process
	The law of opportunities	Stouffer 1940	a migrant is established in a certain place determined by factors of the conjuncture but in any place can be found factors of positive, negative and neutral influence for the migration decision
Contemporary theories	Neoclassical economic theory	Sjaastad 1962	the relationship between migration and investment in human capital
	The theory of the world system	Wallerstein 1974	migrants from poor countries move to rich countries
	Genealogical theory	Harbison 1981	migration is a family decision
	Neoeconomic theory	Stark 1993	migration is a family strategy
	Network theory	Massey 1990	the development of networks determines the formation of the social capital of migration
		Gurak 1992	
Massey 1998			
Institutional theory	Massey 1998	migration has led to the establishment and/or development of international companies, institutions and voluntary organizations	
	Jennissen 2004		

Source: by the author

As can be seen, synthetically, from the presentation of the theories on migration carried out in table 1, scientists are looking for theoretical answers, describing the reality of migration, but modern theories are in fact a combination of classical and neoclassical theories. Therefore, we are living in a period in which the necessity of finding new perspectives of migration theories is becoming increasingly pronounced.

Of the contemporary theories of migration, the neoeconomic one states that migration is a family strategy, the family occupying an important place in the value system regarding the quality of life of the individual, the resources being obtained by sending a person/s from within the family to work. Because the decision is made within the family, according to this theory, the individual is no longer the only one to decide, and his family is the one that conditions the behaviour of the migration (Stark, 1993; Iancu, 2011).

Network theory examines migrant networks as a form of social capital (Massey, 1990), which is formed through the expansion of networks. This theory (Gurak, 1992) argues that migrants have created support networks by providing newcomers with support, information, emotional and social support, finding a job and earning a decent income. The networks of migrants are dynamic and one of the main themes of the researchers in the field of migration, because migration is closely related to family, friendship or neighbourhood relations, the migrants choosing their place of destination depending on the presence of relatives, friends or neighbours present at place of destination. The first writing about migrant networks as a form of social capital (Massey, 1990), shows that it was first formed in 1987.

Migration is a human phenomenon that constantly characterizes the evolution of humanity, the migratory movements being in an increasing trend and with a very diversified spatial footprint, the maximum level being reached after the Second World War, with the development of the systems of distance transport. According to the World Bank, between 1950 and 2015, the world's population tripled, rising from about 2.5 billion in 1950 to over 7.7 billion in 2015 (European Commission). In parallel with the population growth process, the process of migration of people across the globe, the rapid means of transport favoring the territorial travels to distant distances. In the contemporary context, international migration takes place on the following routes: Africa - Europe, Asia - Europe, South America - North America and Europe, Mexico - US In this context, the factors that determine the cumulative character of international migration (Massey, 1998), and which are found, for example, are also highlighted.

- in the starting space (distribution of household income at community level, land distribution and the way of organization of agriculture, migration culture, regional distribution of human capital),
- in the destination area (social equity),
- but also, in both areas (migrant networks and institutions).

In the international media, we find explanations regarding the phenomenon of external migration, mainly oriented to the necessity of carrying out an economic activity, more than the desire to change the natural environment or the domicile (Albu, 2007). From this perspective, the European Union promotes circular migration through the EURES agreements, which is a “network of cooperation between European public employment services, created to facilitate the free movement of workers within the European Area and Switzerland”. Currently, in the space of the European Union, Romanians have legal status of free movement and residence.

3. The link between migration and development

The contemporary era can certainly be called an era of migration. In recent years, international migration has been unprecedented. Globally, it reaches over 232 million people or 3% of the world’s population, and 740 million people are considered internal migrants (Petrozziello, 2013). The migratory phenomenon is characteristic, practically, of any state. Migration has become a defining feature of the modern global economy, and the main factors underlying its expansion are the processes of globalization, technical progress, the new economic order, etc. The importance of contemporary migration is linked not only to the number of those who migrate, but also to the fact that the migration phenomenon has become a global one and takes on increasingly diverse forms. People travel for varying periods of time, but shorter. They adopt a pattern of circulatory migration, continue to maintain strong links with the place where they left or practice unregulated migration. Women are increasingly present in migration (feminization of migration occurs).

Many families adapt to a transnational life, and the effects of migration are becoming more and more important. Globally, the amounts sent to the countries of origin reached values that were hard to imagine in the past. However, with their return home, migrants bring not only money, but also new ideas of development, knowledge and new entrepreneurial skills acquired through migration. In this way, the migrants clearly contribute to the modernization of the country and play an extremely important role in its intellectual and economic development. Since the early 1970s, the governments of some countries have seen international migration as a major instrument of economic development. Migration is no longer a phenomenon that affects only those who leave, but equally, those who remain in the country of origin, and those in the country of destination. Due to migration, entire areas transform and change

their ethnic and cultural identity. Thus, contemporary migration has become one of the fundamental elements of social and economic transformation in the contemporary world (Iancu, 2011).

However, migration can also cause negative effects, such as the “brain drain”, the decline and aging of the population, the deterioration of social security systems, leaving home without care for children and the elderly, trafficking in human beings, etc. Therefore, migration is neither good nor bad, and the aim of migration policies should be to increase the positive effects and mitigate the negative ones of migration. In other words, one of the current tasks of public authorities in the field of migration management would be to integrate migration processes into development strategies. However, despite the increased importance given to the relationship between migration and development, at present, national migration policies have not yet succeeded in fully exploiting its benefits, as they have not been integrated into development strategies.

Empirical research shows that migration can be an important factor in development for both migrants and their households. One of the most popular theories (the neoclassical one) demonstrates this connection, according to which, the differences of development stimulate the migration, which, in turn, contributes to a relative levelling of the rate of development between the countries of origin and those of destination. For this reason, the development impact of migration, at aggregate, community or national level, tends to be more tangible for the country of origin than for the country of destination (Petrozziello, 2013).

Analysing the evolution of the relationship between migration and development, de Haas proposes a periodization of the interpretation of the migration-development relationship. If in the 1960s it was believed that migration contributes to development through the transfer of resources from the country of destination to the one of origin (financial remittances, knowledge), thus “modernizing” the regions of origin of migrants, in the 1970s (after the oil shock of 1973) she was accused of fuelling the global gaps, by transferring cheap Labor to the developed regions, as well as from the “brain drain”, and during the 1980s and 1990s empirical research showed that migration is not influenced only by the factors economic, but also social ones related to the way of life.

In 2006, the United Nations (UN) debates in general the connection between migration and development and decides to initiate annual meetings on this topic (Global Forum or Migration and Development) (Petrozziello, 2013; European Commission). Generally, when the citizens of a state actively decide to migrate, their incomes tend to increase, and the opportunities also manifest themselves in other ways (gaining new skills, assuming new social roles and

responsibilities by migrant women). Moreover, the free and independent decision to migrate can also be considered the application of a fundamental human right - the right to free movement. The right to free movement can be a real opportunity to extend freedoms and, consequently, to increase the level of human development. Although not all the impact of migration is positive (for example, many migrants may have problems of integration in a new social environment or increasingly the problem of children of migrants left home without care), as a rule, “voluntary” migration is beneficial for the development of the migrant both economically and socially.

Returning migrants to the households they maintain relationships with, systematic transfers tend to improve their lives and increase the quality of life and migrants, and their family members. These transfers can result in higher incomes for households, more resources for expenses related to health, education, housing, etc (European Commission). They can offer households and other types of benefits such as new ideas and knowledge. These transfers are also important from the human rights point of view, as they can provide the financial and non-financial resources necessary for the realization of fundamental rights (access to education, healthcare, etc.).

Although most “transfers” by migrants to their countries of origin are predominantly private, targeting individuals and households, they have broader implications (CDEP, 2020). For example, remittances sent by a migrant may allow the family to invest in a new home, thus stimulating employment in the construction sector in that locality. Also, a person who returns to the country after studying abroad brings with them competences that will benefit the community as a whole. Thus, international migration generates three types of transfers, each influencing development in different ways. The three types of transfers are also called the 3Ts (Iancu, 2011). The first is the transfer of people - the migration itself (T1). This includes immigration, emigration and return. The second type is the transfer of know-how and knowledge (T2).

As they move, people take with them ideas and knowledge, forming new skills and ideas while abroad. This “knowledge capital” can circulate between the countries of origin of the migrants and the countries of destination through social networks. The third type is the transfer of financial assets (T3), which can take various forms: salaries, savings, remittances, as well as investments. Transfers of type 2 and 3 may also come from those who are not migrants themselves, but members of the diaspora. The effects of 3T can be both positive and negative. Thus, in the case of T1 transfers, employment abroad can reduce unemployment in the country of origin, while also contributing to cover a

possible shortage of labor force in the country of destination. At the same time, this transfer leads to the disintegration of the family in the country of origin or it can generate various conflicts of ethnic or national character, as well as pressures on the social protection system and on the infrastructure of the countries of destination, due to the increase of the population number. In the case of T2 transfers, migrants may transmit certain attitudes and values to households and communities in the country of origin. And these can be positive (in case of cultivation of new traditions focused on health protection or investment in education) or negative (when these transfers generate a flow of human capital from the country of origin). In the case of T3 transfers, the members of the families of the migrants can significantly improve their standard of living. At the same time, the inflow of remittances can stimulate inflation and increase the inequalities between households that receive remittances and those that do not.

Transfers generated by international migration can also be interpreted through the notion of capital. Thus, the resources and benefits with which international migration contributes to development are embodied in human capital, financial capital, social capital and cultural capital.

The financial capital is manifested through the remittances of migrant workers from abroad. In the last decade, this type of capital has been given more attention both by the authorities of the countries of origin and by the international bodies promoting the idea of integrating migration into the development strategies of the countries of origin due to the enormous volume of remittances received by the country. developing countries (\$580 billion in 2014). Remittances are private funds or in-kind transfers made by migrants to nonmigrant relatives. In addition to the cost, speed, accessibility and security of the transfer services, the mode of sending the remittances is also influenced by the level of information and financial culture of the senders and the recipients.

Remittances are an additional source of income for households and increase the standard of living. Because remittances stimulate consumption, they can have a multiplier effect in local economies. At the same time, remittances produce dependency relationships for members of the families of migrant workers, inequalities between the incomes of migrant families and families without migrants. Human capital is manifested by the professional skills and knowledge that migrants have gained by working abroad. In the same context, entrepreneurial skills or self-confidence, qualities very necessary for personal development in a competitive economy, can be

mentioned. But international migration can also have the opposite effect. In the situation where the migrants obtained the qualifications in the country of origin, but they went abroad, because at home they could not be realized, there is a loss of human capital through the phenomenon of “brain drain” (Iancu, 2011).

The loss of capital also manifests itself in the situation where a highly qualified person going abroad performs unqualified work, taking into account the phenomenon of “brain waste”. However, it is generally acknowledged that the benefits of knowledge tend to be divided between the countries of origin and destination. Thus, skilled migrants, using their skills, will receive higher wages abroad which will turn into remittances. Working abroad, skilled migrants have the opportunity to acquire new skills and knowledge that they can use at home. In other words, there is a transfer of intelligence, a phenomenon that is called “brain gain” (Iancu, 2011).

The social capital is manifested in the social links between the localities of the countries of origin and those of destination that the migrants form and maintain. Namely, social capital allows the creation of networks that facilitate the flow of information, skills, financial resources, values, ideas, etc. between the countries of origin and the countries of destination.

Social capital connects migrants with diaspora associations, contributes to the creation of professional and business networks, etc. Many believe that these links may become weaker as migrants integrate into the social environments in which they have settled. On the contrary, migrants tend to maintain these links by engaging in various development actions (investments in social capital), seeing in them a potential benefit in the future.

The cultural capital that manifests itself through the new values, ideas, behaviours, lifestyles that the migrants cultivate coming to the country of destination. Thus, the quality of life of migrants will increase markedly by acquiring these new values and behaviours (for example, democracy, equity, etc.). The transfer of cultural capital can take place through the contribution of migrants to peace-building and conflict resolution in the countries of origin. The contributions of migrants depend on the extent to which they realize their rights and capabilities as a result of migration. As such, migration is a form of manifestation of the freedom of people who must make the most of it. At the same time, migration can also lead to a decline in well-being if the decision to migrate was made by force (for example, in the case of trafficking in human beings).

4. Migration policies of the European Union

The development and promotion of migration policies within the European Union began in the 1950s, when the foundations of the European Union were laid. The agreements concluded at that time between the countries of the European community were aimed at regulating the migration processes by harmonizing the policies in the field between countries (Albu, 2007). At the same time, the Member States of the European Union were not yet ready to give up entirely the national approaches to migration policies and to promote a common migration policy (Burian, 2009). From that moment on, the migratory processes have undergone several radical structural and qualitative transformations, now becoming a kind of “pendulatory movement”, due to the continuous development of transport and the means of communication. Since the first years of the 21st century, within the European Union, there has been a need to reformulate migration policies in accordance with the new demographic and economic conditions.

The current content of the EU’s migration policy in accordance with the provisions of the GAMM pillars is as follows (Burian, 2009):

a) Legal labor migration

This pillar focuses on improving current legislation and administrative practices in order to increase labor mobility within the European Union. Particular attention is drawn to increasing the level of employment in correlation with ensuring social protection, gender equality and social inclusion. The integration of legal immigrants is a priority of the European Union and implies their access to education and vocational training. The policy of the European Union for the management of labor migration aims to produce flexible admission systems, adaptable to the needs of the Member States of the European Union, which will allow migrants to fully exploit their skills. In this context, the following tools are applied:

- Directive on the “Blue Book” (Council Directive 2009/50 / EC of May 25, 2009, on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for employment of highly qualified jobs);
- “Single Permit Directive” (Directive 2011/98 / EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of December 13, 2011, concerning a single procedure for applying for a single permit for third-country nationals for the purpose of residence and employment in the territory Member States and a common set of rights for third-country workers legally staying in the territory of a Member State);

b) Illegal migration

The European Union is analysing this subject in the light of specific measures for employers who accept undeclared workers, as well as by raising funds for an efficient and humane return policy for migrants, in accordance with the provisions of the “Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union” adopted in 2012. Most of the illegal migrants have entered the European Union legally, on the basis of a short-term visa, but for economic reasons they were also withheld after the expiry of the validity period of the residence visa.

Another issue related to illegal migration is trafficking in human beings. In this context, in 2010 the European Commission appointed a European Union Coordinator for anti-trafficking in human beings and launched a website on anti-trafficking measures taken by the European Union to improve the collaboration and coherence between the actions of the institutions, the agencies of the Union. European, non-EU member countries and international actors involved in combating trafficking in human beings (INSSE, 2017).

5. The evolution of migration in Europe

According to statistics compiled by the World Bank, the population of Europe has grown, from 667 million people (European Commission, 2019). in 1960, to 911 million people, at the beginning of 2017. On January 1, 2018, the population of the European Union (EU) was estimated at 512.6 million, compared to 511.5 million on January 1, 2017, according to data published by Eurostat. In 2017, almost 50% of Europe’s total population is concentrated in five countries: Germany (82.8 million inhabitants), France (67 million inhabitants), Great Britain (62.8 million inhabitants), Italy (60.5 million and Spain (46.5 million inhabitants) (European Commission, 2019).

With regard to the migrant population, Eurostat shows that on January 1, 2016, the total number of migrants was highest in Germany (7.2 million), Spain (5.7 million), England (4.2 million), Italy (3.9 million) and France (3.7 million). In 2010, the ranking did not undergo major changes, most migrants living in the EU were in Germany (7.2 million), Spain (5.6 million), Italy (4.6 million), England (4, 5 million) and France (3.8 million). Together, foreign nationals from these five Member States represented 77.3% of the migrants living in the EU-27. The large number of immigrants from these countries is also preserved in 2018, due to the living conditions and job opportunities offered by these countries. The emigration to the countries of Western Europe for economic reasons, has registered spectacular increases since 1990, mainly due to the fall of the communist regime (Burian, 2009)

It is estimated that only Eastern and Central Europe generate about 850,000 people annually. In the last two decades, Germany, the United Kingdom, France, Italy and Spain have faced a large number of migrants, coming from underdeveloped or developing countries, so it is noticeable that at present, Western European countries are destination countries for immigrants, even if in the past centuries they were sources of emigration (European Commission, 2019).

The same feature is also found in the North European countries (Finland, Sweden, Ireland and England); but alongside the Central European countries (Denmark, Germany, Belgium, Austria, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and France), and the Mediterranean countries (Italy, Spain, Portugal and Greece) which are the central core of migration in Europe; these economically developed countries have experienced the transition from migrant supplying countries to receiving countries.

6. Conclusions

In the following decades, international migration remains a real process and can vary, taking into account political and economic changes, technological and social innovative changes, increasing demographic imbalance, the effects of climate change and globalization trends.

In order to increase the positive effects and to minimize the negative effects in the field of labor migration, the following aspects can be identified: stimulating the return migration and the circular labor migration; creating favorable conditions for returning migrant businesses and developing SMEs in regions; adapting national educational policies to the needs of the labor market; the more active and effective involvement of the diaspora in development policies.

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